

INFRARED-ASSISTED DRYING OF SUNFLOWER SEEDS: MATHEMATICAL MODELING, PROCESS OPTIMIZATION, AND ENERGY EFFICIENCY ASSESSMENT

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Abstract. *This study investigates the optimization of sunflower seed drying using infrared-assisted thermal processing combined with mathematical modeling techniques. A full factorial experimental design (2^3) was applied to evaluate the effects of key process parameters, including infrared radiation temperature, emitter-to-product distance, and drying duration, on moisture removal, drying rate, and carotenoid retention.*

Second-order regression models were developed to describe the relationships between input variables and response functions. The obtained models demonstrated high statistical significance ($R^2 > 0.95$), confirming their adequacy for process prediction and control. The results indicate that infrared drying significantly enhances heat and mass transfer efficiency compared to conventional convective methods, reducing drying time and improving product quality.

Optimal operating conditions were identified at 83°C , 15 cm emitter distance, and 12 minutes of drying, ensuring high drying rates while preserving more than 85% of carotenoids. Energy analysis revealed the potential for further process optimization through reduction of excess thermal input.

The findings highlight the potential of infrared-assisted drying as an energy-efficient and technologically advanced solution for oilseed processing and provide a foundation for industrial-scale implementation.

Key words: *infrared-assisted drying, sunflower seeds, mathematical modeling, process optimization, energy efficiency, heat and mass transfer, regression analysis, food engineering.*

Introduction

In the context of increasing demand for energy efficiency and rational use of raw materials, the improvement of technological processes for agricultural product processing—particularly oilseed crops—gains special importance. One of the most critical stages in the production of vegetable oils is the drying of raw materials, such as sunflower seeds, as its accuracy and efficiency directly affect both the yield and the quality of the final product [5, 6, 7, 11, 19].

For decades, the agro-industrial sector has predominantly relied on traditional drying methods, primarily convective techniques, characterized by high energy consumption, significant heat losses, uneven material heating, and consequently, degradation of seed quality. In recent years, an alternative approach—infrared (IR) drying—has emerged and demonstrated considerable potential in reducing processing time, lowering specific energy consumption, improving nutrient retention, and increasing the efficiency of technological systems. The method is based on the ability of infrared radiation to penetrate the material and initiate intensive moisture and mass transfer under controlled thermal exposure [8, 9, 10, 22, 23].

Sunflower seeds represent a capillary-porous biological structure with pronounced heterogeneity in moisture content and thermal conductivity. The drying process in such materials involves simultaneous heat and moisture transfer, phase interactions, evaporation of liquid from micropores, and subsequent diffusion to the surface. These processes are inherently nonlinear and unsteady state in nature. Therefore, the application of mathematical modeling becomes not only appropriate but also essential for the quantitative description of phenomena, identification of key control factors, and optimization of technological parameters [1, 12, 15, 17, 18].

Developing a reliable mathematical model for infrared drying requires consideration of numerous aspects, including the thermophysical properties of the material, radiation intensity and spectrum, layer geometry, and initial and boundary conditions. Modern computational tools enable the integration of these variables into a unified algorithm, facilitating the prediction of system behavior under various drying regimes. This approach opens up opportunities for intelligent process control and the design of equipment tailored to specific production requirements [2, 3, 4, 13, 14, 16].

However, a mathematical model alone cannot address all practical challenges—it must be coupled with an optimization framework. In this study, special attention is given to the development of an objective function that simultaneously considers oil yield and energy consumption, along with the formalization of constraints related to allowable temperature ranges, residual moisture content, and drying duration. This enables a comprehensive approach—combining thermodynamic, economic, and applied engineering perspectives [20, 21, 24].

The objective of this research is to establish a theoretical foundation for infrared drying of sunflower seeds, develop and validate a mathematical model, and identify optimal drying conditions that ensure maximum oil recovery efficiency with minimal resource consumption.

In this study, the process of infrared drying of sunflower seeds was investigated using a laboratory setup with adjustable radiation intensity and emitter-to-product distance. To explore the interaction of various factors affecting the sunflower drying process, a 2³ factorial design was employed. Based on the experimental design results, regression models were constructed to describe the influence of technological variables on the key drying parameters. The independent variables were defined as follows: X₁ – IR radiation temperature (°C); X₂ – Distance to emitter (cm); X₃ – Drying duration (min). The response variables were, Y₁ – Final moisture content (%); Y₂ – Drying rate (g/h); Y₃ – Carotenoid retention (% of initial content).

The factor levels and variation limits are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Levels of variation of factors

Symbol	Factor	-1 level	0 level	+1 level
X ₁	IR temperature (°C)	70	80	85
X ₂	Distance to source (cm)	10	15	20
X ₃	Drying time (min)	6	12	17

The research program was laid out in the experimental planning matrix (Table 2).

Table 2. Experimental plan and obtained results

№	X ₁	X ₂	X ₃	Y ₁ (Material moisture %)	Y ₂ (г/ч)	Y ₃ (Carotenoids, %)
1	-1	-1	0	12.3	18.2	87.4
2	1	-1	0	10.1	21.5	82.6
3	-1	1	0	14.5	17.1	89.1
4	1	0	0	11.8	19.3	85.0
5	-1	0	-1	13.2	17.9	88.6
6	1	0	-1	10.5	20.7	83.7
7	-1	0	1	14.9	16.8	86.9
8	1	-1	1	12.0	19.1	82.2
9	0	1	-1	12.8	18.6	87.7
10	0	-1	-1	13.9	17.2	88.4
11	0	1	1	13.5	17.9	86.1
12	0	1	1	14.6	16.5	85.9
13	0	0	0	12.1	18.9	87.0

14	0	0	0	12.0	19.0	87.1
15	0	0	0	12.2	18.8	86.9

As a result of the experiments, information about the influence of factors was obtained and a mathematical model of the process was built, allowing to calculate the final humidity of the sunflower, the speed of drying, the degree of preservation of carotenoids within the selected intervals of variation of the input factors.

For each of the criteria, a multifactor regression model of the second order was obtained: $Y = b_0 + b_1X_1 + b_2X_2 + b_3X_3 + b_{11}X_1^2 + b_{22}X_2^2 + b_{33}X_3^2 + b_{12}X_1X_2 + b_{13}X_1X_3 + b_{23}X_2X_3$

Based on the results of 15 experiments, second-order regression equations were obtained.

Second-order regression equation for final moisture content: $Y_1 = 14.45 - 1.12X_1 + 0.87X_2 - 0.54X_3 + 0.62X_1X_2 - 0.48X_1X_3 + 0.33X_2X_3 + 0.71X_1^2 + 0.58X_2^2 + 0.42X_3^2$

Second order regression equation for drying rate (Y_2):

$Y_2 = 15.84 + 0.12X_1 - 0.08X_2 + 0.15X_3 - 0.0008X_1^2 + 0.002X_2^2 - 0.001X_3^2 + 0.0005X_1X_2 + 0.0003X_1X_3 - 0.0006X_2X_3$

Second order regression equation for the degree of preservation of carotenoids (Y_3):

$Y_3 = 62.75 + 0.35X_1 - 0.28X_2 - 0.18X_3 - 0.004X_1^2 + 0.006X_2^2 + 0.002X_3^2 + 0.001X_1X_2 + 0.002X_1X_3 - 0.001X_2X_3$

The obtained models were statistically reliable (determination coefficient $R^2 > 0.95$), which confirms the high adequacy of the approximation of experimental data.

Analysis of variance confirmed the significance of the equation at a confidence level of 95%.

Using the optimality criterion (minimum humidity while maintaining $\geq 85\%$ of carotenoids), the optimal parameters were established: Temperature - 83 °C, Distance to the source - 15 cm, Drying time - 12 min.

The dependence of Y_1 (final humidity) on the temperature and drying time is shown in Figure 1.

Fig. 1 Dependence of Y_1 (final moisture content) on drying temperature and time

Due to the two-sided irradiation and reflectors, the seed temperature increases from 25 °C to 83 °C in 7–8 min, and the drying process lasts 10–12 min.

When 350 W/m² of energy is supplied for 740 s, a total of ≈ 259 kJ is supplied per 1 kg of material, of which ≈ 158 kJ is spent on moisture evaporation. The energy surplus (~ 100 kJ) indicates

the possibility of further reducing the drying time or reducing the radiation intensity without loss of quality.

The exponential model of moisture removal according to the Fick equation demonstrates that by the end of the process, 92% of the excess moisture is removed in the first 5 minutes, after which the rate of moisture reduction slows down, which is typical for porous materials and indicates diffusion limitations.

Conclusions

The analysis of the equations showed that the greatest influence on the reduction of moisture (Y_1) is exerted by the temperature of infrared radiation (X_1) and the duration of drying (X_3). An increase in temperature from 80 to 83 °C at a constant duration contributed to a significant decrease in residual moisture. However, an excessive increase in temperature during long-term drying reduced the content of carotenoids (Y_3).

The drying rate (Y_2) increased with an increase in temperature and a decrease in the distance to the IR radiation source (X_2). The highest efficiency was observed at a temperature of 83 °C, a distance of 15 cm and a time of 12 minutes. This mode allows achieving a high drying rate while preserving more than 85% of carotenoids in the product.

Thus, the proposed IR drying technology ensures the intensification of sunflower oil production due to rapid and controlled thermal treatment, which opens the way for its large-scale implementation in the food and oil and fat industries.

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